

GRADUONOMY IN THE GRAMMATICAL AND SEMANTIC CATEGORIES OF THE VERB IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article explores the phenomenon of graduonomy within the grammatical and semantic categories of verbs in the English and Uzbek languages. Graduonomy, as a subtype of semantic gradation, reflects the hierarchy and intensity of meanings expressed through verbal forms. The research aims to identify how different levels of meaning, modality, and intensity are encoded in verb categories such as tense, aspect, voice, and mood. The comparative analysis draws attention to cross-linguistic similarities and discrepancies that emerge in representing verbal gradation. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of typological distinctions and help refine language teaching and translation strategies.

Keywords: graduonomy, verb categories, semantics, grammar, English, Uzbek, aspect, modality, comparison

In linguistic studies, the concept of graduonomy refers to the semantic gradation or scaling between linguistic units within a specific category. While often applied to adjectives and adverbs, its application to verbs—particularly in relation to grammatical and semantic categories—has received limited scholarly attention. In the context of English and Uzbek, two typologically distinct languages, this concept offers unique insights into how languages express gradation in action, state, and modality. A comparative-descriptive method was employed to analyze verb-related graduonomic structures in English and Uzbek. Examples were drawn from corpora, literary texts, dictionaries, and grammar manuals.

Verbs are a part of speech characterized by a complex system of grammatical categories.

The various verb forms, which differ in specific meanings but are united by a common semantic core, collectively form the system of grammatical categories that express actions. The system of grammatical forms unique to verbs determines their grammatical categories. Regardless of whether a verb functions as a main predicate or otherwise within a sentence, it must belong to at least one of the grammatical categories specific to verbs. These categories

include voice, mood, tense, person-number, and polarity (affirmative/negative forms) [1].

The data reveal that both English and Uzbek demonstrate graduonomic structures in their verb systems, though the means of expression differ significantly. English primarily uses analytic structures and modal auxiliaries, while Uzbek employs morphological gradation, reduplication, and lexical compounding.

For example, English relies on tense and aspect combinations (e.g., has been doing implies more persistence than did), whereas in Uzbek, the use of intensifying morphemes or verbs achieves a similar effect (e.g., ko'rib chiqmoq, ko'rib chiqib chiqmoq).

Moreover, modality in both languages reflects complex gradations of certainty and obligation, but Uzbek structures allow for more layered and culturally nuanced expressions—such as those indicating social politeness or indirection.

In addition to being subject to semantic gradation, verbs can also differ in the degree of certain features within their grammatical categories. Among Uzbek linguists who have studied graduonymy, only O. Bozorov has briefly addressed the issue of gradation at the morphological level in his research, where he explains that gradation exists even within the categories of verbs. Below, we will analyze how gradation manifests within these categories. First, we will examine how graduonymy appears in the category of voice, based on the views of various researchers.

The voice category of verbs serves to fill and define the verb's subject valency, adapting the action to the communicative context. Based on how the action relates to the subject and object, several types of voice are distinguished. In modern Uzbek, the main types of verbal voice include the active (default) voice, reflexive, causative, reciprocal, and passive, each formed with specific derivational suffixes.

O. Bozorov, in his research, presents gradation within the voice category based on various principles, particularly considering the degree of involvement of the subject in the execution of the action. According to his analysis, the following types of graduonomic sequences can be observed among voice forms:

a) By the degree of the subject's involvement in the action:

active/reflexive → reciprocal → causative → passive

b) By the increasing number of external participants involved in the action:

reflexive → causative → reciprocal

c) By the degree of external influence on the action:

neutral (active, reflexive, passive) → cooperation or equality (reciprocal) → subordination (causative)

d) By the decline in the clarity or definiteness of the action:
active → reflexive → reciprocal → causative → passive

This analysis illustrates how graduonomy can be traced across the voice category in the Uzbek verb system, highlighting the nuanced relationships between forms and their semantic-functional load [5.184].

In her doctoral dissertation, S. Mukhamedova examined the semantic characteristics of various action verbs in the Uzbek language, including the differences between semantic units (sememes). Since our research focuses specifically on the phenomenon of graduonomy within action verbs, we find it appropriate to include her classification [6.122].

According to her, within the semantic field of “covering an object”, verbs such as yopmoq (to cover), burkamoq (to wrap), qoplamoq (to overlay), kiymoq (to dress), yo‘rg‘aklamoq (to swaddle), ko‘mmoq (to bury), ilgaklamoq (to hook-shut), tambalamoq (to barricade), qulflamoq (to lock), and zanjirlamoq (to chain-shut) are used. Among them, verbs like ilgaklamoq, tambalamoq, qulflamoq, and zanjirlamoq involve specific instruments (such as hooks, locks, and chains), thus implying a stronger degree of the 'covering' meaning. She emphasizes that these verbs also exhibit semantic differences, which are illustrated in the following examples:

Ilgaklamoq – “to shut by hooking.”

Example: Ilgakni ilib berkitmoq – “She hooked the door shut.”

Sentence: Eshikni ilgaklab kel – “Hook the door shut.”

Tambalamoq – “to barricade using a beam or bar.”

Example: Tambani qo‘yib berkitmoq – “We shut the door and blocked it with a large beam.” (From G‘afur G‘ulom)

Qulflamoq – “to lock using a padlock or key.”

Sentence: Mirzakarimboy locked the gate as he arrived. (From Oybek)

Zanjirlamoq – “to shut or secure using a chain.” Sentence: Hasanali laid down in the guest room and chained the gate. (From Abdulla Qodiriy)

These examples illustrate graduated semantic distinctions within a single semantic field, where the instrumentality and intensity of the action increase the strength of the 'covering' meaning in each verb.

When discussing the grammatical nature of verbs, it is important to emphasize that the verb is an independent part of speech, expressing action,

state, or process. Verbs are classified as an independent word class based on several distinctive features.

In English linguistics, the concept of graduonymy has primarily been explored from a semantic perspective, while its grammatical dimension remains largely unexamined. In our study, which investigates gradation within the grammatical categories and semantic groups of verbs in Uzbek and English, it is essential to reference the current state of research on verb categorization in English.

According to available linguistic descriptions of the English verb, the primary grammatical categories include: the category of person and number, the category of tense, the category of aspect, the category of voice, the category of mood

Considering that only two types of voice are distinguished in English—active and passive—and that no intermediate voice forms exist between them, it becomes clear that gradation similar to what is observed in Uzbek is not present in this category. Therefore, the voice category in English does not exhibit internal gradation based on meaning, as it does in the Uzbek language [7.42].

The mood category is a grammatical category that reflects the verb's relation to reality as intended or perceived by the speaker. It represents the morphological expression of modality, indicating whether the action or state expressed by the verb is real or hypothetical. According to English linguists, modern English has three main moods, which are:

The Indicative Mood – expresses factual statements

The Imperative Mood – expresses commands or requests

The Subjunctive Mood – expresses wishes, hypothetical or non-real actions

The indicative mood in English indicates that the action took place, is taking place, or will take place based on real, factual conditions. Therefore, it is often referred to as the factual or realis mood.

The imperative mood, by contrast, does not confirm the reality of the action, but rather conveys instructions or requests.

The subjunctive mood expresses non-real, imagined, or hypothetical actions. There are two main types of the subjunctive in English—typically referred to as present subjunctive and past subjunctive, although their distinctions relate more to mood than tense. Based on this, we can establish a graduonomic scale of English verb moods progressing from realis to irrealis states:

Indicative mood → Imperative mood → Subjunctive mood

This gradation can be illustrated through the verb save:

I saved some money. (Indicative)

Save the money! (Imperative)

God save you. (Subjunctive)

Graduonomy in verbal systems offers a valuable framework for understanding how languages organize and express degrees of action and modality. The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek reveals that while both languages encode graduonomic distinctions, the linguistic tools employed are different due to their structural typologies. These findings contribute to contrastive linguistics, translation theory, and second language pedagogy by highlighting the semantic depth behind verbal categories in both languages.

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